

Full length article

The tubular cavity of tobacco mosaic virus shields mechanical stress and regulates disassembly

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Tobacco mosaic virus
TMV
AFM
Biomechanics
Disassembly
Nanotubes
Mechanical fatigue
Nanoindentation
Coarse-grained simulation
Von mises stress
Finite Elements Simulations

ABSTRACT

Here we probe Tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) particles immobilized on a solid surface under transversal mechanical stress. We use atomic force microscopy to implement punctual deformation with high force (~nN) that induces immediate virus rupture (single indentation assay), and continuous cycles of low force (~100 pN) that generate a gradual disassembly of the virus particle (mechanical fatigue assay). These experiments are interpreted with the help of TMV coarse-grained and finite elements simulations, which indicate that the tubular cavity screens the transmission of mechanical stress from the top to the bottom half of the virion structure. Likewise, mechanical fatigue experiments reveal how TMV disassembles following growing transversal rifts with different dynamics that depend on a combination of the applied force and the tubular geometry of the virus. Our results indicate how the cylindrical cavity of TMV cushions the lower half of the virus structure from mechanical stress and regulates mechanical disassembly.

Statement of significance: The inability of plant viruses like tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) to infect mammals makes them ideal for technological applications. While TMV is known for its durability, it's unclear if this is due solely to its capsid proteins or its tubular structure. Using Atomic Force Microscopy, coarse-grained and finite elements models, we found that the tubular hole screens the transmission of mechanical stress from the top to the bottom half of the virion structure. This characteristic induces a stepwise disassembly process from intact to half virus, finishing in the virion disruption. Since the energies between proteins are comparable to those of other viruses, there is a protective effect of the tubular cavity that transcends the size down to the nanoscale.

1. Introduction

Tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) was the first virus ever reported [1,2] and one of the first biomolecular structures to be observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) in 1939 [3]. TMV has become a work-horse for research [4–10] due to its simple helical structure, durability, and ease of purification [8,11]. More recently, TMV has attracted remarkable interest in the field of bioengineering [6,12] due to its various applications in energy storage [13], as nanotemplate [13–16], in drug delivery [8,17], in biocatalysis [18] and for sensing applications [19]. The advantage of biological nanostructures lies in the

difficulty of producing artificial counterparts accounting for a regular and homogeneous molecular design solely through chemical or physical methods. The very nature of the biological synthesis of nanostructures offers high precision and control in building uniform protein architectures [14].

TMV structure is composed of a long tube-shaped protein coat of 300 nm in length, with an external diameter of 18 nm and a central cylindrical cavity of 2 nm in radius. The coat consists of 2130 copies of the TMV Coat Protein (CP) arranged in helical symmetry [10]. A single-stranded RNA is buried in the inner protomers of the capsid, located at 4 nm in distance from the center of the hollow tube (Fig. 1A

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2025.04.012>

Received 22 November 2024; Received in revised form 1 April 2025; Accepted 3 April 2025

Available online 4 April 2025

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and 1B). Also, several TMV particles (virions) can aggregate longitudinally (Fig. 1C) [20]. The long rod-like structure offers a large surface area for interacting with inorganic compounds or organic molecules introduced by point and insertion mutations, making them useful as biotemplates [21]. For example, TMV enhances contact with analytes, thereby amplifying signal generation and improving the sensitivity of devices [14]. In addition, TMV is endowed with extraordinary physicochemical properties to withstand a wide range of environmental conditions, such as temperature [22], pH [11,14], humidity [23,24], pressure [25], and ultrasound [26,27]. In this context, significant efforts have been made to comprehend the TMV biomechanics [4,20,28], including finite elements (FE) modelling [15,29]. However, little attention has been paid to the mechanostuctural determinants of TMV and disassembly, which is key for understanding virion stability [30]. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) has proven to be a powerful tool for exploring the structure and biophysical properties of soft matter [31], particularly biological protein structures in native conditions [32,33]. Indeed, the study of viral structures has been a central focus of AFM research, with the objective of elucidating the complex interplay between mechanical properties, function and structure [33–36]. In a complementary way, theoretical modelling can provide details that are not accessible by AFM [37–39]. In the case of TMV, simulations have been previously carried out using FE methods [15,29,40]. While FE has been useful to understand how the TMV structure deforms under mechanical stress, it has certain limitations; for instance, the continuous nature of FE impairs the description of fracture and collapse phenomena which are well known in AFM experiments [39,41,42].

Here, we use AFM to conduct single indentations and mechanical fatigue assays on TMV capsids immobilized on a solid surface. We also aim to interpret these experimental results with FE and novel particle based coarse-grained (CG) simulations that elucidate the response of TMV capsids to mechanical stress. Overall, this work seeks to address the determinants of the endurance TMV structure.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. AFM

Experiments were carried out with a sample of TMV, 10 mg/ml in 10 mM sodium-potassium phosphate buffer, which we diluted one hundred times (0.1 mg/mL) in TN buffer (Tris 10 mM, 140 mM, pH 7.5). Subsequently, 30 μ L of the diluted solution was deposited onto Highly Oriented Pyrolytic Graphite (HOPG) [43,44]. After a 20-minute incubation period, the substrate was rinsed three times with pure TN buffer, resulting in a final volume of 120 μ L in the AFM liquid cell.

The single indentation assay experiments were accomplished by

using the stiffest cantilever of qp-BioAC (Nano and More) probes. These cantilevers have a rectangular shape with a symmetric tip measuring <10 nm in radius. Prior to the experiments, the spring constant (nominal 0.2 N/m) of each cantilever was calibrated using the Sader's method in air [45]. The single indentation assay consists of poking the immobilized virion at a single spot while recording the normal force against the Z-piezo displacement. This information can be converted into a force-indentation curve (FIC) [35,46] to gather mechanical parameters such as the spring constant, breaking force, brittleness, etc. To convert cantilever deflection into force, it is necessary to perform indentations on a hard surface (in this case, the HOPG). The slope of these curves gives us the sensitivity of the cantilever in each experiment [47]. It ranged from 5 to 12 nm/V. Using this value and the spring constant of the cantilever, we can convert the cantilever deflection (V) into force (nN) and the piezo deformation (nm) into tip displacement in the Z-axis (nm).

Mechanical fatigue experiments were conducted with OMCL-TR400PSA-1 probes, which are triangular cantilevers with a pyramidal tip of \sim 15 nm in radius. Their calibrated spring constants, again measured by the Sader's method ranged from 0.065 to 0.110 N/m. Since in our experiment the AFM scans run from left to right, the left uphill side of any structure (adsorbed on the HOPG) is prone to damage [48]. We always aligned our x scan to the virions to minimize this effect.

AFM imaging was carried out using Nanotec Electrónica S.L., Madrid, Spain, in Jumping Plus Mode [48]. In this mode, the tip approaches the sample at each pixel until a certain normal force is reached. At this point, the Z-piezo retracts in order to disengage from the surface, and the tip moves laterally to the next pixel. This method allows precise control of the applied force and minimizes the lateral dragging force exerted on the viruses. All images and curves were processed and analyzed using WSxM software [49].

2.2. Coarse grained simulation of TMV

In all-atom models [37,38,50] which are widely used for protein simulation [51], each atom is represented explicitly. However, TMV is a very large system even without water molecules (\sim 6,800,000 atoms) [52], and simulations of AFM nanoindentation are associated with large characteristic times (\sim 2 s) [53]. Coarse grained (CG) models provide a computationally feasible alternative, as in this description a set of atoms is represented by a single bead. Each CG bead is subjected to a set of potentials which take into account the protein structure and the effective interactions with the rest of the system and the environment [54–56]. In this way, although less detailed than all-atom approaches, CG models can overcome computational limitations by reaching just the necessary complexity to understand TMV deformation and breakage. Over the years, several CG models have been developed to study viral capsids,

Fig. 1. TMV structure and AFM imaging. (A) 3D model showing the helical protein capsid as well as the ssRNA inside, obtained from PDB 4UDV [10]. (B) Axial view of the model. (C) An example of a topographic image of several TMV obtained with AFM. Virions can link with each other, forming particles longer than 300 nm, while others are broken or not completely assembled. Individual TMV particles are highlighted inside white dashed circles and longer structures correspond to aggregation.

their mechanical properties and their response to external forces. Early models of viral elasticity, inspired by shell theories, emphasized the non-continuous nature of capsids and provided insights into certain mechanical properties, such as the stress distribution [57], but these models lacked molecular details and had limitations. Among the first studies to investigate viruses using particle-based models, which allow for a more detailed analysis of mechanical processes, the work conducted by Klaus Schulten's group stands out [58,59], in particular, simulations of viral capsid indentation via AFM [53]. The use of CG models for studying the mechanical properties of viruses has been employed for years [39,41,60], demonstrating their ability to enhance the resolution of AFM experiments [61,62]. Currently, studies on HIV stand out, as these simulations have been crucial in determining that the mechanical properties of the virus could play an essential role in the infection process [63–65].

Despite the existence of a variety of CG models for proteins [66], we choose the so-called alpha carbon resolution models [67,68]. In these models, each amino acid is represented by a single bead at its alpha carbon position, while both water and ions are implicitly represented by incorporating their effects into the interaction potentials. At this level, CG models can reproduce the deformation of large protein assemblies under mechanical inputs as well as fracture formation, while significantly reducing the computational cost, when compared to all-atom simulations [39,41]. Within the family of alpha carbon models, we employ the self-organized polymer (SOP) model [68] (Fig. S1A). The SOP model represents each residue by a single bead centered at the CA position, omitting chemical details and non-native contacts. Although this means it does not model explicitly side-chain or solvent-mediated interactions, this simplification is justified in our case because in large systems the distribution of native contacts, e.g. the distribution of energy, is more critical than their chemical nature [41,69,70]. Due to the vast number of native contacts involved in the deformation of such structures, assigning an average energy and approximating their distribution is sufficient; an approach effectively implemented in SOP [60]. Moreover, the higher resolution provided by other popular models such as Martini (≈ 3 beads per amino acid) [71] or SIRAH (≈ 4 beads per amino acid) [56,72] does not substantially alter the energy distribution that ultimately governs the mechanical response. In contrast, their increased computational demand makes them less practical for simulating large viral assemblies. In addition, SOP has been successfully applied in previous studies to investigate the mechanical properties of viruses and to reproduce AFM experimental results [60,61,73]. Moreover, it has been demonstrated to be an effective method for calculating the stress distribution when viruses are subjected to mechanical deformations [74], making it particularly suitable for our TMV study.

To simulate the AFM indentation process, the tip is represented as a sphere with the nominal radius of the AFM tip (~ 10 nm). This sphere is tethered with a harmonic potential (Fig. S1B), thus mimicking the spring constant of our cantilever (0.2 N/m) [60].

In the SOP model a bead is placed at each alpha carbon of the protein structure (Fig. S1A). Consecutive beads in the sequence are connected by a finite extensible nonlinear elastic (FENE) potential and are covalently bonded:

$$U_{FENE} = - \sum_{\text{covalent}} \frac{kR_0}{2} \log \left(1 - \frac{(r_{ij} - r_{ij}^0)^2}{R_0^2} \right),$$

where $k = 14$ N/m is the bond spring constant, $R_0 = 0.2$ nm is the maximum allowed deviation from the equilibrium bond length and r_{ij}^0 is the equilibrium distance, determined by the crystal structure. The model adds two additional interactions that depend on the definition of native contacts. Native contacts are pairs of amino acids far away in the sequence that interact specifically and maintain the 3D structure of the protein. While multiple definitions of native contacts exist [69,70], the SOP model employs a simple distance-based criterion using the

crystalline structure. Specifically, two amino acids are considered to interact if their respective alpha carbons are within 8 Å in the crystal structure and are separated by more than two covalent bonds in the sequence [68]. In this case, the amino acids interact via a Lennard-Jones like potential:

$$U_{\text{Native Contact}} = \sum_{\text{native}} \epsilon_{nc} \left[\left(\frac{r_{ij}^0}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - 2 \left(\frac{r_{ij}^0}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right],$$

where r_{ij}^0 is the distance between the amino acids in the crystal structure and ϵ_{nc} is the interaction energy between these amino acids. Conversely, if two amino acids are separated by more than two positions in the sequence but do not form a native contact, their interaction is governed by a simple steric potential:

$$U_{\text{Non Native}} = \sum_{\text{non native}} \epsilon_{nn} \left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{ij}} \right)^6,$$

where $\sigma = 3.8$ Å and $\epsilon_{nn} = 1$ kcal/mol. This model biases the protein's state towards the folded, crystallographic configuration. The remaining parameter to determine is ϵ_{nc} , which corresponds to the average interaction energy between amino acids in native contacts. While other authors typically determine ϵ_{nc} through all-atom simulations of the structure [73], we adopt a different approach. We simulate several indentation curves, slightly varying the value of ϵ_{nc} within a range of values compatible with those used in other studies, and we select the one that most closely mimics the experiments. Once ϵ_{nc} is determined, this value is employed for the rest of the simulations. We use the protocol described in Kononova et al. to calculate the stress. Specifically, we conduct simulations at $T = 0$ and represent the von Mises stress [74]. Simulating at $T = 0$ more clearly demonstrates how the structure distributes stress and how different geometries affect its distribution.

The model has been implemented in UAMMD [75,76], which performs the simulation entirely on a GPU, resulting in high performance. For the simulations, we employed a Langevin integrator at $T = 300$ K (except for stress calculations at $T = 0$), specifically using the BBK integrator [77–79]. A friction coefficient of 0.2 ps⁻¹ was used; this coefficient is considerably lower than the actual coefficient in water. We use this value to employ the Kramers turnover technique, allowing for more efficient sampling of different configurations [80]. Finally, the tip indentation velocity is set to the optimal rate to guarantee reproducibility. To determine this velocity, we begin with high indentation speeds and gradually decrease them until the indentation curves converge.

2.3. FE simulation of TMV

Finite elements simulations of the FIC on TMV were performed using the COMSOL Multiphysics program. Two types of geometries were implemented. In the first case, a homogeneous tube with an outer radius of 9 nm and inner radius of 2 nm, mimicking the geometry of TMV; in the second case, a solid homogeneous cylinder with the same radius (9 nm) as TMV, but without the internal cavity. The cylindrical objects were placed lying flat on top of a rigid flat substrate and indented by a rigid sphere with a radius of 15 nm, representing the AFM tip used in the experiments. The length of the simulated cylinder was 80 nm. The model was reduced to a quarter using two planes of symmetry and meshed using a total of 50 K quadrilateral elements. The indentation process was simulated by solving the nonlinear elasticity equations for different fixed values of the spherical tip height. Since the precise value of the Poisson's ratio of TMV is not known, we have used a value of 0.3 which is customarily used to describe protein materials [15,29]. A Young's modulus value of 0.14 GPa was selected by fitting the resulting hollow cylinder FIC to the average experimental curve.

3. Results

3.1. Single indentation assay

After localizing a convenient TMV particle (Fig. 2A), we conducted 1 to 3 indentations under constant speed (~ 50 nm/s), at random locations of the virion top, far away from the tube edges and previous indentations, if any. The indentation of an intact TMV tube (Fig. 2A, left) results in the tube division (Fig. 2A, right).

Then, we use the experimental FICs (Fig. 2B, black) to parametrize the CG model by testing interaction energies ϵ_{nc} of 1.1 kcal/mol, 1.2 kcal/mol and 1.3 kcal/mol in theoretical FICs (Fig. 2B, red from bottom to top) carried out on the CG TMV structure (Fig. 2C) with a 10 nm radius tip. This range of ϵ_{nc} encompasses the energies used in other studies [60,61,73,81]. We found that $\epsilon_{nc} = 1.2$ kcal/mol (thick red line) showed the best correlation with experiments (Fig. 2B, thick black line) and was used in all subsequent CG simulations.

The virtual AFM FIC helps to interpret the different stages of the experiment (Fig. 2). Until reaching ① the cantilever does not bend. Once the tip establishes contact with the virion at ①, the force increases almost linearly while the virion undergoes an elastic deformation [35] until ② (Fig. 2B). The slope of this regime can be ascribed to the virion spring constant or stiffness [82]. At juncture ②, the upper capsid breaks into two different parts (illustrated by a dashed line in the sketch of Fig. 2C) and begins to separate, with one piece being subducted inwards and the other piece being pushed outwards. Simulated FIC shows how the upper half of the virion breaks first (Fig. 2C). During this process the capsid becomes softer; the tip penetrates faster in the virus structure until the upper and bottom walls collide at ③ (commonly known as breaking point). Upon reaching this stage, the capsid structure is significantly disrupted. The mechanical load over the proteins of the subducted side becomes so large that it leads to another rupture (dashed line in sketch ③ of Fig. 2C). This rupture effectively divides the TMV capsid into two halves, which can be easily separated allowing the tip to reach the bottom wall at ④. Afterwards, the tip compresses the bottom half of the virion until most proteins have been removed (Fig. 2C). The indentation at this stage, where the force increases rapidly, corresponds to the original virion height, ~ 16 nm on average. This value is lower than the diameter of the virion due to a small deformation upon virus

adsorption (Fig. 2C) [83]. Additionally, the FIC progression varies after juncture ②, presenting a second breaking point in approximately 40 % of the curves. This phenomenon is described in Fig. S2.

To explore the mechanism by which the tube is divided by the FIC, we plot the longitudinal profiles before and after FIC (Fig. S3). These profiles reveal that the indented virion (red) exhibits a lower length than the initial structure (black). The lower length is due to the loss of a few CPs of the TMV structure at the cracks.

FIC data provide significant information about the mechanical properties of the virion [33,35,46]. The slope between ① and ② represents the spring constant of the virion, which is 0.7 ± 0.2 N/m (Fig. 3A). The force required to break the capsid is 2.4 ± 0.3 nN (Fig. 3B), and the critical deformation is close to 4 nm (Fig. 3C), matching the diameter of the internal cavity (Fig. 1B). These results suggest a crucial role of the central hollow region in the resilience of the virus.

3.2. Mechanical stress distribution

Using the parameterization of ϵ_{nc} obtained before (Fig. 2B), we compute the stress distribution within the TMV structure. The von Mises stress for different stages of the indentation process is represented in Fig. 4 (SV1 and SV2). Before the indentation begins, only the bottom of the TMV structure is subjected to minimal strain due to the virion interaction with the substrate (Fig. 4A) [83,84]. However, as the tip pokes the virion, the upper half of the protein capsid undertakes most of the deformation and stress. This is – at least qualitatively – also found in experiments and in a simple mechanical theory of the radial deformation of thick-walled tubes [85]. When the tip establishes contact with the virion (Fig. 4B) and moves down, the upper half of the virion is homogeneously stressed (Fig. 4C), while the bottom proteins are almost unaffected: they only experience significant stress when the inner walls collide (Fig. 4D). Simulation indicates that the upper capsid breaks earlier due to uneven accumulation of mechanical stress (Fig. 4, SV1 and SV2). FE simulations also help to ponder this uneven stress distribution. Fig. 5 represents the von Mises stress of FIC in a TMV-like tube (Fig. 5A) and in a solid cylinder of the same outer radius (Fig. 5B) for an indentation of 2.7 nm. For better clarity, only values of the von Mises stress greater than 1×10^7 Pa are represented in a color scale, showing that the

Fig. 2. Single indentation assay. (A) Experimental AFM image of a single TMV before (left) and after (right) the FIC. (B) Experimental FICs (black) compared with coarse-grained simulated FICs (red) on the TMV capsid with a 10 nm radius tip. In total, there are 39 experimental FICs on virions and 3 computational simulations on TMV with different interaction energies between amino acids: 1.3, 1.2, and 1.1 kcal/mol (from top to bottom, red). Henceforth, 1.2 kcal/mol will be exclusively utilized for the next figures (red dot) as it yields the best fit. The numbers denote the key events along the most representative FICs (thick lines). (C) Structural alterations occurring within the TMV capsid during these specific events in the simulation.

Fig. 3. Mechanical properties of TMV from FICS. (A) Spring constant in the elastic regime of TMV. (B) Force required to irreversibly damage the protein capsid. (C) Maximum indentation the virus can withstand without irreversible damage.

Fig. 4. Coarse grained simulation plotting the von Mises stress of TMV under an indentation in transversal (up) and longitudinal (bottom) orientations. (A) No tip-capsid contact. (B) First contact; only the area close to the tip is being affected. (C) Deeper indentation; all the upper capsomers are highly stressed. (D) Gap cavity closure; the whole structure is being compressed and is about to break. Support video in SV1.

Fig. 5. Finite elements simulations. (A) Nanoindentation in a hollow cylinder with an outer radius of 9 nm and an inner radius of 2 nm. (B) Nanoindentation in a solid cylinder with an outer radius of 9 nm. In both cases the indentation is 2.7 nm and the von Mises stress is indicated by coloured contours and filtered to show only values greater than 1×10^7 Pa.

bottom part of the TMV-like tube experiences a significantly smaller stress than the upper half in contact with the AFM tip.

3.3. Mechanical fatigue and gradual disassembly

Above we described stress evolution, deformation and rupture of the TMV structure during local deformations with a single indentation assay. We now turn to exploring the effects induced by mechanical fatigue on the TMV structure.

In *jumping plus mode* [48], the imaging process for each pixel involves approaching the tip to the sample until a preset force is reached. Afterwards the z-piezo retracts out of contact from the sample and moves to the next pixel to repeat the cycle. Thus, a topographical map of the TMV particle is completed by applying a normal force well below the breaking force (~ 2.5 nN, Fig. 3B) and avoiding lateral dragging forces.

Then, virus particles can lose individual capsomers during repeated imaging at constant forces of few hundreds of pN, inducing disassembly and cargo release [30,46,86]. Mechanical fatigue of TMV induces rifts along the capsid (Fig. 6A, #10) that grow over time until the virion disappears (Fig. 6A, bottom, SV3 and SV4). We carried out fatigue assays at 150 pN (9 virions), 200 pN (9 virions), 250 pN (10 virions), and 300 pN (8 virions).

Although rifts occur at both low (150 pN) and high forces (250 pN), experiments demonstrate that virions can withstand more cycles at low forces (~ 100 frames) than at high forces (~ 50 frames, Fig. S4). Beyond this difference, the dynamics of virion disassembly also changes. From AFM images, we calculated a kymogram, depicting the longitudinal topographical profile of the virion over time (Fig. 6B). The AFM tip erodes the virus particles, inducing rifts that initially correspond to the lack of individual or few CPs. Subsequently, the scanning of the AFM tip also releases the neighboring rift CP subunits, increasing the rift widths in an unzipping process. At high forces (≥ 250 pN), the loss of CPs takes place suddenly, once the rifts have coalesced (~ 40 frames, Fig. 6B left), and the virion disappears after ~ 50 frames. However, at low forces (~ 150 pN) disassembly occurs gradually, losing all the CPs only after ~ 100 frames (Fig. 6B right). To highlight the differences between both dynamics, we have converted the data of the kymograms into density plots (Fig. 6C, in both cases, the data until the first rifts appear have been removed to focus on the disassembly process). Here, we can observe a significant difference (Fig. 6C): at high forces, disassembly occurs suddenly in a single step from intact to collapsed structures, while at low forces, an intermediate step is present at mid-height of the virion.

4. Discussion

In this paper, first we provide a basic yet comprehensive understanding of the mechanics of adsorbed TMV particles (virions). Second, we study the parameters that determine the mechanical resistance of

Fig. 6. TMV disassembly with mechanical fatigue. (A) Sequence of AFM images at 250 pN (left) and 150 pN (right), indicating the frame number from top to bottom. The corresponding supplemental videos can be found in SV2. (B) Kymograms showing the evolution of the central longitudinal profiles marked with dashed lines at frames #1. (C) Density plots of the kymograms along disassembly. Red areas indicate higher concentration of points while indigo areas the opposite.

TMV to be crucial for applications in materials science. And third, we induce and analyze the TMV mechanical disassembly.

During single indentation assay TMV mostly holds its general structure even after reaching the yield point (⊙, Fig. 2). Experiments show that once the yield point is reached, the tip still must exert more force (0.5 ± 0.5 nN) before achieving the breaking point. This phenomenon can be illustrated through CG simulations. As the tip pokes the capsid, the upper half of the virion bears the largest part of the deformation and mechanical stress. The tip-capsid contact region undergoes significant deformation, until mechanical stress affects uniformly the

upper half (Fig. 4B and 4C), while the proteins of the lower virion half remain almost unstressed. The stress accumulation induces structural failures that grow over time, generating a crack that quickly induces the collapse of the topmost coat proteins (Fig. 2C, ⊙). Beyond this point, a section of the capsid subducts in the central cavity (Fig. 2C⊙). Now the mechanical stress propagates to the bottom half. Thus, the TMV cavity leads the stress to be accumulated in the upper half, protecting the lower capsomers. We do not observe a different response depending on the region of the virion where the indentation is performed. These differences, if any, are too subtle to be detected with the large variability of

the indentation data. A different approach should be taken in the future to study the distribution of resistance along the TMV. Additionally, when tip-virion contact is established (Fig. 2B, ⓐ), the force increment is not as sharp as found for other viruses [33,87]. TMV shows, instead, a smoother slope. Interestingly, simulations suggest that this behavior is due to the protruding residues of the CPs (about 1.6 nm) [11], which are softer than the rest of the capsid (Fig. S5).

We conclude that TMV strength is supported by both its high stiffness (~0.7 N/m, Fig. 3A) and its fatigue resistance. This endorses TMV as a relative stiff virus compared to other virus particles, such as HSV-1, MLV, HIV-1, Influenza virus, hPBV, MVM or TGEV with 0.33 N/m, 0.31 N/m, 0.22 N/m, 0.04 N/m [33], 0.27 N/m [86], 0.55 N/m [88], 0.01 N/m [89], respectively. In parallel, our results show that TMV can withstand both larger fatigue forces (2–4 bigger) and 5 times longer resistance periods compared to other viruses [30,86]. This finding is in line with the general observation of a high mechanical resilience [25–27], a phenomenon that should also operate during natural transmission, e.g. in soil [24], and that is used for controlled infections in plant pathology experiments.

Does the mechanical resistance stem from the biochemical composition or its tubular geometry? Simulations suggest that the interaction between amino acids is ~1.2 kcal/mol. This value is similar to other viruses [73,81,61], indicating that the chemical interactions between TMV coat proteins are comparable to those in other virus structures. Therefore, the tubular geometry is most likely the major responsible of TMV biomechanics. This geometry helps to uniformly dampen the mechanical stress in surface adhered virions, allowing the upper proteins to elastically yield into the cavity. Hence, tubular geometries (aside from TMV) appear to be convenient for bioengineering applications [14,90]. The CG model of a single indentation assay provides the details of the CP deformation and stress, revealing the screening role of the cavity (Fig. 4). To obtain further evidence of this computational insight, we can refer to the mechanical fatigue results. When using high force values (~250 pN), the TMV structure undergoes a sudden drop of the height to ~0 nm (Fig. 6C, left). This fact indicates that the mechanical stress is affecting all the CPs, leading to their immediate collapse. In contrast, at low forces (~150 pN), the TMV disassembly shows an intermediate plateau at 7 nm height (Fig. 6C, right), that persists for ~30 frames. Afterwards, the virion structure collapses after ~25 additional frames. The height of the intermediate state coincides with the thickness of the TMV wall (Fig. 1A). Therefore, mechanical fatigue at low force applies mechanical stress mostly to the upper half of the virion, like in the simulations (Fig. 4C). In mechanical fatigue experiments, the lower virion half remains screened during the first stage of disassembly (Fig. 6C right, up to frame ~30). Once the upper half is lost, the lower CPs begin to be removed. As happens in single indentation assay experiments, fatigue indicates that the cavity dampens mechanical stress, protecting the lower part of a surface immobilized virion.

In further support of this notion, our FE simulations compare the mechanical stress in a tube (Fig. 5A) and in a solid cylinder (Fig. 5B) with the same Young's modulus (0.14 GPa) derived from FIC (Fig. 2B). These simulations aim to clarify whether the stress distribution is caused by the central cavity. The results of Fig. 5 for the 2.7 nm FIC (before the first rupture) clearly show that high mechanical stress reaches the lower half in a solid cylinder (Fig. 5B). In contrast, in a tubular shape, the downward stress propagation is stopped by the central cavity (Fig. 5A). Therefore, the FE results indicate that the presence of the cavity is responsible for the screening of the stress.

We can compare this behavior with that of other tubular structures, such as microtubules. Despite having a tubular structure and similar interaction energies (~1.0–1.9 kcal/mol) compared to TMV (~1.2 kcal/mol) microtubules are observed to be relatively softer, ~0.07 N/m [81, 91]. This can be attributed to the low radial ratio: microtubules have an inner diameter of 15 nm and an outer diameter of 25 nm, resulting in a radial ratio of $\alpha = 25/15 \approx 1.7$, which is significantly lower than that of TMV, $\alpha = 4.5$. A macroscale analogue are thick-walled polymer tubes

[85]. To our knowledge, other microscale thick-walled tubes have not yet been analyzed in similar detail.

A significant difference to usual mechanical disassembly is the formation and expansion of cracks in the TMV structure. Previously, a similar phenomenon was reported [4], probably due to high-force imaging. Taking the discussion a step further, we can draw parallels between natural and mechanical disassembly processes. TMV disassembly is chemically induced with high pH and low calcium concentrations during infection [53,92]. These conditions remove protons and induce repulsion between the negatively charged carboxylate-carboxylate and carboxylate-phosphate pairs, thus destabilizing the TMV structure, inducing uncoating of CPs [93–95]. Our experiments do not allow to observe whether mechanical disassembly can induce ion pair formation or other chemical changes, such as removing protons or calcium ions. We aim at probing the stability of TMV for its biotechnological use. However, we might speculate that the thorough deformation of CPs during tip-induced disassembly could lead to increased CP-CP approaches, and the associated forces may lead to a complete change in the chemical nature of a CP.

Distribution of mechanical stress and disassembly patterns highlights the importance of tubular geometry, determining the response of the viral capsid to mechanical stress. While practical applications of TMV do not involve AFM tip poking of the virion, the collisions with the capsid induced by molecular crowding [96] or the stress due to cellular uptake [97] would have similar effect as mechanical fatigue. More generally, handling virions in non-natural environments (e.g. in technical applications) will always result in mechanical stress. In extreme cases, this can lead to disassembly into fragments of <300 nm length by using ultrasonics [26,27], which are also accessible in controlled ways [90]. Conversely, it is also plausible to mutate TMV in order to obtain longer rods [98]. Overall, this work demonstrates the role of the hollow region in halting stress propagation in protein tubes, an effect that can transcend the size up from the nanoscale. Our results highlight the relevance of tubular shapes for increased endurance in nanotechnology. We believe that our insights contribute to elucidate the mechanisms underlying viral stability and potential vulnerabilities that may either be exploited, or have to be considered for applications in materials science [6,12–15]. For instance, the protection of the inner cavity is particularly useful for drug delivery. Therapeutic cargo can be loaded into the inner cavity of TMV, as it has already been accomplished in vitro for cancer therapy [17]. In closing, our work underscores how the tubular geometry of protein aggregates can have a stronger influence than the very nature of the molecular interactions in their mechanical response.

Data availability

All relevant CG simulation data have been uploaded and is available in two separate files. Part 1 can be accessed at <https://zenodo.org/records/14,982,795> and Part 2 at <https://zenodo.org/records/14,983,110>. Additionally, the source code and simulation scripts required to reproduce the simulations are freely available on GitHub at https://github.com/PabloIbanez/TMV_CAVITY.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

A. Díez-Martínez: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **P. Ibáñez-Freire:** Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis. **R. Delgado-Buscalioni:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **D. Reguera:** Software, Methodology. **A.M. Bittner:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **P.J. de Pablo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

P. J. d. P. acknowledges support by grants PID2021–126608OB-I00, the Human Frontiers Science Program (HFSPO RGP0012/2018) and SI3/PJI/2021–00216. D. R acknowledges funding from grant PID2021–126570NB-I00 (MINECO/FEDER, UE). Authors also thank the Spanish Physical Virology Network RED2022–134654-T. AMB is grateful for a sample donation by C. Wege, Universität Stuttgart. AMB was supported by grants EU-MSCA 101072645 nanoremedi, EIC-pathfinder 101115292 (“textadna”), MINECO PID2023–147987OB-C32 (“IVIS-AID”), and Dip. Foral Gipuzkoa (“shifte”). RDB acknowledges funding from Spanish Agencia Estatal de Investigación under the project PDC2021–121441-C2 and through the “María de Maeztu” Program for Units of Excellence in R&D (CEX2023–001361-M). We further acknowledge the help of Dr. Aitziber Eleta (nanogune) in preliminary experiments.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.actbio.2025.04.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2025.04.012).

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